

Advancing Integration and Reuse Across Diverse Scholarly Data Sources. Introducing the SKG-IF: the Interoperability Framework for Scientific Knowledge Graphs

Andrea Mannocci¹, Paolo Manghi¹, SKG-IF WG²

¹*CNR-ISTI, Pisa, Italy*

²*RDA*

Purpose

Scientific Knowledge Graphs (SKGs) are pivotal in organising, linking and sharing actionable insights from the vast and ever-expanding corpus of research information, such as literature, research data and software, funding information, and contributing organisations, to support various stakeholder needs, such as discovery, reuse, reproducibility, validation, monitoring, statistical analysis, impact assessment, and evaluation (Sugimoto & Larivière, 2018; Waltman, 2019; Aryani et al., 2020; Rafols et al., 2024).

Despite their inherent transformative potential, SKGs are often built with a specific use case at hand and a siloed mindset. Notwithstanding the value of an individual SKG, achieving interoperability across diverse SKGs is a persistent challenge, and it is crucial to unlock their full potential and ensure the seamless integration and reuse of locally available information and enhancements, and enable synergic collaboration across different scientific domains and institutions (Aryani et al., 2020).

The RDA Working Group on the Scientific Knowledge Graph Interoperability Framework (SKG-IF) was established to address such endeavour. This talk will highlight the significance of interoperability across SKGs, outline the work carried out by the RDA WG on the SKG-IF, and summarise the group's output in providing a foundation for a more cohesive and interoperable future for scientific knowledge representation.

Methods

The development of the SKG-IF was guided by a collaborative, multidisciplinary approach facilitated through the Research Data Alliance (RDA). The adopted methodology included:

- **Stakeholder Engagement:** Since its incubation, the WG has engaged with and onboarded a diverse set of stakeholders, including SKG providers, such as Crossref, DataCite, OpenAIRE, OpenCitations (Peroni & Shotton, 2020), OpenAlex (Priem et al., 2022) and EuroCRIS, researchers, data practitioners, and technologists, to capture a broad spectrum of requirements and challenges related to SKG interoperability.

- **Landscape Analysis:** In its first phase, the WG systematically reviewed the prominent existing SKGs and their respective information models. This preliminary study served to highlight the main entities modelled, their properties and relations and come to an agreed-upon least common denominator of key pieces of information that can be of interest for interoperability.
- **Iterative Framework Development:** The WG built and maintains the SKG-IF through iterative cycles of design, feedback, and refinement to ensure robustness and adaptability.
- **Community extension:** To address special use cases and applications, the WG devised a mechanism for introducing extensions to the SKG-IF, whose lifecycle falls outside the WG scope (see below).
- **Implementation and Validation:** Testing the proposed framework through pilot projects to validate its applicability and efficacy across different domains and use cases.

Results

The RDA WG's SKG-IF output is a comprehensive and actionable framework addressing interoperability challenges and a set of resources openly accessible through the SKG-IF website, which include comprehensive documentation, practical examples, and reference implementations to facilitate adoption by the community.

The SKG-IF Data Model is the metadata model used for the data that is compliant with the SKG-IF Interoperability Framework. The SKG-IF Data Model is used to model all the SKG-IF main entities, their attributes and their relations to other entities. All these aspects are implemented using the "language" of the Semantic Web, in particular by re-employing several existing ontological models developed to address specific modelling scenarios compatible with the aims of SKG-IF.

The SKG-IF Data Model allows one to record information about the following SKG-IF entities, which are:

- Research product, which may be of four types - research literature (such as articles, conference papers, thesis, peer-review, blog posts, books, and reports), research data, research software, and other digital assets, uniquely identified, whose nature does not fall in the first three categories;
- Agent, representing an individual (e.g., a person, an organisation, or another kind of entity being able to act) who is involved in the creation, publication, dissemination, etc. of a research product;
- Data source, describing a service or platform where a research product (its metadata and files) is stored, preserved, and made discoverable and accessible;
- Grant, which describes funding awarded to an agent by a funding body;
- Topic, which represents the scientific disciplines, subjects and keywords potentially relevant for a research product; and
- Venue, which models a "publishing gateway" used by an agent to make their research products available to others.

The SKG-IF Data Model has also been implemented as an OWL ontology, i.e., the SKG-IF Ontology (SKG-O). It is not yet another bibliographic ontology, but rather a place where existing and complementary ontological entities from several other ontologies, all employed in SKG-IF, are grouped together to provide descriptive metadata compliant with the SKG-IF Data

Model. The ontology is composed of six different ontological modules, formally imported into it, one for each type of SKG-IF entity.

The SKG-IF data created following the Interoperability Framework are aligned with the SKG-IF Ontology via the SKG-IF JSON-LD context. In addition, a specific SHACL document has been developed for semantically validating the data provided according to the data model.

The SKG-IF includes specifications for implementing basic APIs, which for the time being focus on resolver functionalities, i.e., returning an SKG-IF compliant representation upon providing a list of IDs to resolve. Therefore, the endpoints the SKG-IF describes at the moment comprehend:

- GET https://my.skg.io/list_schemes provides a comprehensive JSON list of the IDs and PIDs schemes that the API is willing to resolve. The local scheme refers to IDs that are valid locally in the SKG at hand, and should always be present (e.g., ['local', 'doi', 'orcid', 'handle', 'cordis', 'openalex']).
- GET <https://my.skg.io/resolve/<schema>:<id>> which resolves a couple <schema, id> and returns the SKG-IF representation of the relevant object.
- POST <https://my.skg.io/resolve> works as the method above, while passing a list of couples <schema, id> to be resolved in the body of the request.

As anticipated in the Methods section, both the SKG-IF core model and the API specifications can be extended by engaging with the extension mechanism devised by the WG.

Introducing extensions to the SKG-IF serves as a strategic step towards addressing the evolving and diverse needs of scientific communities and projects. The concept of extensions within the SKG-IF is designed to cater to shared interests and requirements that the existing standard entities and properties may not fully meet.

By allowing for the development of extensions that enrich the core model entities of the SKG-IF, the framework can accommodate specialised use cases, specific research needs, and emerging data requirements without compromising the integrity and structure of the core framework. Extensions offer a way to further develop the framework's capabilities without disrupting existing entities, maintaining compatibility, coherence, and interoperability across diverse datasets and knowledge graphs.

Provided that an extension embodies shared interests and needs (e.g., from a project, community, or domain) rather than isolated requirements, and does not tamper with or disrupt the entities and APIs already defined in the SKG-IF specifications, it can extend the core in the following ways:

- Extending core entities: New properties and relations can be added to existing core entities to address the needs outlined in a specific case statement.
- Introducing new entities: Extensions can define brand-new entities with structures and semantics distinct from core entities. No core entity should act as a super-entity of community-defined entities.

Furthermore, an extension can enhance the API specifications by:

- Defining additional HTTP parameters and their expected behaviour to customise the core API resolver methods specified by the SKG-IF.
- Introducing new API methods with advanced functionalities and custom behaviours.

An SKG-IF extension's lifecycle (i.e., development and maintenance) falls outside the scope of the RDA WG and the discussion around the core model. Therefore, delivering an extension can be fast-paced as long as it meets the expected degree of clearness and compliance. Once an extension is mature enough and has been adopted in the intended contexts, the WG can consider and cherry-pick part of the covered aspects for inclusion in the SKG-IF core model.

Value

The SKG-IF represents a significant advancement in addressing the fragmentation and silos prevalent in the landscape of Scientific Knowledge Graphs. By providing a unified approach to interoperability, the framework empowers stakeholders to:

- Enhance cross-domain research and collaboration by enabling seamless integration of diverse SKGs.
- Improve the reusability and discoverability of scientific data through standardised semantic alignment and interoperability profiles.
- Accelerate innovation by reducing technical and organisational barriers to knowledge graph interoperability.

Furthermore, the SKG-IF lays the groundwork for future developments, including automated interoperability solutions, AI-driven knowledge discovery, and global-scale data integration initiatives. As such, it serves as a cornerstone for advancing open science and data-driven research in the 21st century.

References

- Aryani, A., Fenner, M., Manghi, P., Mannocci, A., & Stocker, M. (2020, August). Open science graphs must interoperate!. In *International Conference on Theory and Practice of Digital Libraries* (pp. 195-206). Cham: Springer International Publishing. https://doi.org/10.1007/978-3-030-55814-7_16
- Peroni, S., & Shotton, D. (2020). OpenCitations, an infrastructure organisation for open scholarship. *Quantitative Science Studies*, 1(1), 428–444. https://doi.org/10.1162/qss_a_00023
- Priem, J., Piwowar, H., & Orr, R. (2022). OpenAlex: A fully-open index of scholarly works, authors, venues, institutions, and concepts (No. arXiv:2205.01833). arXiv. <https://doi.org/10.48550/arXiv.2205.01833>
- Rafols, I., Meijer, I., & Molas-Gallart, J. (2024). Monitoring Open Science as transformative change: Towards a systemic framework. *F1000Research*, 13, 320. <https://doi.org/10.12688/f1000research.148290.1>
- Sugimoto, C. R., & Larivière, V. (2018). *Measuring research: What everyone needs to know*. Oxford University Press.
- Waltman, L. (2019). Open metadata of scholarly publications: Open science monitor case study (Issue July). <https://doi.org/10.2777/132318>